

treatment 1 and 2.1% in treatment 2) (Table 1). Japonicas generally have a higher efficiency of callus formation than do indicas. Differences in callusing ability and regeneration efficiency between parents and hybrids may depend on factors such as differences in combining ability of parents and varying degrees of heritability.

The amount of embryogenic calli was higher in medium containing ABA than in medium without ABA (Table 2). The calli after subculturing in media with ABA generally appeared whiter, and the embryogenic calli were more defined and developed compared with calli without subculture and ABA preculture treatment.

Plant regeneration was almost twice as great in treatment 2 as in treatment 1, perhaps because more nonembryogenic calli formed as a result of no subculture and preculture treatments with ABA.

This study reveals that certain refined treatments administered after callus induction and prior to regeneration cause increased plantlet regeneration. ■

Pest resistance

Evaluation of selected cultures for resistance to rice tungro disease and its vector, green leafhopper

A. Gosh and N. V. Krishnaiah, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

A set of 81 cultures possessing resistance to at least one insect pest or disease was tested under glasshouse conditions for resistance to rice tungro disease (RTD) and its vector green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant).

The entries were scored at seedling stage (15-25 d old) on 0-9 scales for RTD and GLH using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

We found 18 entries to be promising against GLH; 6 of these showed some resistance to RTD (scores of 4) (see table).

Table 2. Green plant regeneration of parents and F₁ crosses in different medium treatments.

Genotype	Callus plated (no.)	Embryogenic calli (no.)	Nonembryogenic calli (no.)	Embryogenic calli (%)	Plant regeneration (%) ^a
<i>Treatment 1 (without subculture and preculture)</i>					
M201	112	18	94	16.1	1.2
M202	107	15	92	14.0	1.4
IR50	77	7	70	9.0	0.9
M201/IR50 (F ₁)	619	37	582	5.9	0.3
M202/IR50 (F ₁)	508	20	488	3.9	0.4
Total	1423	97	1326	6.1	-
<i>Treatment 2 (with subculture and preculture)</i>					
M201	140	29	111	20.7	2.1
M202	137	29	112	18.2	2.6
IR50	92	11	81	11.9	1.7
M201/IR50 (F ₁)	531	43	488	8.0	0.8
M202/IR50 (F ₁)	716	65	651	9.0	0.6
Total	1616	177	1443	10.7	-

$$^a = \frac{\text{Anthers producing calli}}{\text{Total anthers plated}} \times 100.$$

Reaction of selected cultures for resistance to RTD and GLH.

Designation	Cross	Mean reaction to GLH		RTD reaction ^b (0-9 scale)
		Original ^a (1-9 scale)	Transformed (sq root)	
BPT2217	BPT3329/ARC6650	3.9	2.0	5
BPT4358	BPT3291/ARC6650	1.9	1.4	5
BPT4363	BPT3291/Vellathilcheera	3.2	1.8	5
RP2333-156-8	Ratna/ARC10659	2.9	1.7	6
RP2337-43-4-1	Ratna/IET6858	3.3	1.7	4
RP2541-167-290	Swamadhan/RP1579-36	2.2	1.5	5
RP2547-100-255	ARC5723/ARC6650//RP1579-36	2.6	1.5	4
CRM47	- ^c	2.3	1.5	6
P2409	-	2.7	1.6	5
ASD	-	5.5	2.3	5
Bhoban (OR 447-20)	-	3.0	1.7	6
Cul 8770	-	2.2	1.5	4
Cul 8756	-	2.6	1.6	4
Pusa 598-17-349	-	2.3	1.5	6
IET10810	Pankaj/Mahsuri	3.3	1.8	6
IET11047	Nam Sagui 19/IR5215-301//IR5853-102	2.0	1.4	5
RP2337-46-5-4	Ratna/IET6858	3.1	1.8	4
RP2337-202-93-10	Ratna/IET6858	3.2	1.8	4
IET7302 (resistant check)	-	1.0	1.0	3
TN1 (susceptible check)	-	9.0	3.0	7
LSD (0.05)	-	-	0.6	-
CV (%)	-	-	20.1	-

^aAv of 4 replications. ^bAv of 3 replications. ^c- = not available.